

USE OF EUPHEMISMS IN UZBEK PRESS

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Euphemisms - is created to rename concepts that have already been named in the language, and soft, sweeter words are used instead of harsh, unpleasant words. For example: "stupid" can be replaced by "short minded", "deaf" can be replaced by "hard of hearing", "thief" can be replaced by "crooked hand", "die" can be replaced by "passing away", *do not become a victim, give life*, etc. By using euphemisms, the event takes on a softer tone. For example, when the concept of **dying** is used, a person feels a kind of trembling, a hoof of fear. On the other hand, if other words - euphemisms are used instead of the word die, some positivity is added to the event. Especially the use of euphemisms in the press pages requires skill from the publicist. When we observe the pages of gaeta and magazines, we are sure that euphemisms are more visible in literary-artistic materials. For example, let's take the lexeme to die, which has various variants. The number of synonyms that have arisen as an expression of this concept is very large. This situation can be explained in connection with the human spirit. It aims to mitigate, soften the negative impact of the concept of death, and thereby express sympathy to loved ones:

To die — The time of *the patient's death is determined* ("Dead dear" 2012, March 29), *You will read them after my death* ("Yoshlik" 2012, No. 4), *My month died when I was small, I did not even have a baby* ("Youth" 2010, No. 6), *when I was studying in elementary school, my sister named Zahrokhan and brother named Hamitjon died one after another from severe colds* ("Yoshlik" 2010, No. 11),

Passing away — *My father married me as soon as I returned from the military in 1969, and he died three months later*. When he *passed away*, *my father Abidjon was ten years old, and my aunt Shafolat was five years old* (Yoshlik, 2010, issue 11.)

He completed the servitude — Recently, Nyura's mother *completed the servitude when she was over eighty and nearly ninety* ("Mahalla", March 20, 2010);

Passing away — *My parents passed away one after the other, and I became a worshiper at my uncle's house* ("In the world of law", March 29, 2012),

That's what life is all about, my friend.

Do not slip on the path of goodness.

Life is a blessing, cherish every moment

*This is the **past from the world** ("Capital Transport", May 4, 2012);*

Biting the ground — Although the woman did not lay a finger on anyone, *she bit the ground* on six policemen who were "coming in the front line" ("Yoshlik" 2012, No. 4);

Surrender — Oh God! "Aqbilak fell to the ground and gave up immediately . The reason is that *the soul surrendered* ("Youth" 2012, issue 4);

This lexical combination is sometimes used as a combination **of dead**, which gives some positive color to the reality: *One of the policemen fell out of the car and lay dead* (Yoshlik 2010, issue 4);

Passing away — He *passed away* on April 13 this year at the age of 93 ("Nurani" 2012, April 20);

Lying dead — *One of the policemen fell out of the car and fell dead.* (Youth 2010, No. 4);

The combination of **suicide** shows that **death** is not caused by the Creator, but by the person himself who tortured his body and **died** : **This** was equivalent to the writer's gradual *suicide* (Yoshlik 2010, No. 4);

To leave or **leave this world** — *I would like to put my pages in a cover and glue them so that they can be opened and read only after I **leave this world*** (Youth 2010, No. 4);

Passing away — *My sisters have already **passed away at my father's age*** (Youth, 2010, No. 11);

Saving his life — Amir Temur's personal doctors, the *dovruqli hakim Khazik* took all measures to *save the owner's life* ("Huquk Olamida", April 12, 2012);

The last moment of his life in the phrase when used, it is understood that the death has not yet occurred, but it is certain that this event will happen: *in the camp of Otro governor Berdibek, which is not far from the desert where the soldiers settled, the great master, who spread over seven climates, brought 27 countries under his pen, and ruled the throne of Movarounnahr for thirty-five years, was living **the last moments of his life*** ("In the world of law" April 12, 2012);

Um Shomi tyira tyira borburst' ' is a variant of the concepts "the last moment of his life" and "the last moment of his life" typical of classical literature: *But the*

evening of the general's life was drawing closer and closer , and the angel of death was ready to fulfill the eternal sentence. ("In the world of law", April 12, 2012);

Ajal kismiq – The poor man who *died and rolled into the ditch* (in the world of law, March 29, 2012);

Death led – *Death led the painting to the back of the house, but after all!* (In Legal World, March 29, 2012). These phraseological euphemisms "to kill" and "to lead to death" are effectively used in the sentence to explain and express the event. It can be said that it served to increase his image.

Leaving Dorulfano – The Great Master *left Dorulfano at the age of 69 with the same admonitions* ("Law World", April 12, 2012);

Parting – *In the meantime, Zafarkhojaev lost his motherly care and adviser Zubayda* (Youth, 2010, No. 11). In this place, the word **to die means to die** , forming a homonymic euphemistic series.

To execute – I executed *them , engaged in adultery, cheated* ("Youth" 2010, issue 6). The combination of **execution** in this sentence means that the death was not done by God, but by his servant.

It is known that from the time a person is born, his marriage, life, death, and even his burial have a gradual sequence. There are also euphemisms for these concepts. For example, a person first develops in the mother's womb (fetus) and then is born. Then, after living the life given by the Creator, he dies and is buried. These concepts are skillfully softened and delivered to the reader on the pages of the press:

The word HOMILADOR also forms several lexical-synonymous euphemistic series. For example, words and phrases are used, such as байди балди , **байй бар**, **бай балд**, **бай клат**, **бай бал**, **бай бал** .

Heavy – *If you are heavy when you see Yaquatkhan* ("Khalk sozi" March 8, 2009);

To be tall – When he heard that *I was tall , believe me, he didn't put his hand in cold water* (" Darakchi" 2009);

And euphemisms related to BIRTH are:

Eye opening – *During eight months of last year, 38 women opened their eyes in our maternity hospital* ("Turkestan"), *next month the woman's eyes are expected to open* ("Khabar", May 4, 2012), *After that, they had no appetite for a long time. - when the hour came, his eyes lit up* ("Diydor Aziz", March 29, 2012);

To have children – Mexican citizen Carla Vanessa Perez *is close to becoming the woman with the most twins in the world* ("News" May 4, 2012);

To have a child — *In order to postpone the time when he was not able to achieve it in his youth, he went to **have a child** (Yoshlik, 2010, No. 11);*

a girl or a boy — *The daughter-in-law of the plum teacher **saw a boy** ("Farmer" 2007, issue 1), My son **was born after my daughter** ("Darakchi" 2009)*

We shudder when we hear the word CEMETERY. Even our publicists, writers and poets who are masters of artistic words, use the following euphemisms of this word in their works:

The last destination — *They brought him to **the last destination** ("Turkestan"), except for a distant relative, residents of the village of Qovulbek between the ages of seven and seventy took part in following him **to the last destination** ("Family and Society");*

The last road — *As your local parents say, generous neighbors collected as much money as possible and followed it **to the last road** ("Family and Society" 2012,);*

The last resting place — *During the former regime, various insults and unfair reproaches were poured on the honor of the great commander, even though **the last resting place of Sahibqiran** was trampled and his pure soul was disturbed, but finally the truth was decided. ("In the world of law", April 12, 2012)*

HELP

To bury — *Amir Temur's body was brought to the country's capital, Samarkand, and according to his will, he was **buried** in the magnificent Gori Amir mausoleum, which he built, at the feet of his teacher Syed Baraka ("Huquq Olamida", April 12, 2012);*

We put it on the ground — *A week later, we **put Yodilon on the ground** ("Tashkent truth" February 4, 2012);*

To hand over to mother earth — *I remember very well the day when we handed over his body **to Mother Earth** ("Literature and Art" June 27, 2011);*

Bury — *Babur's body was taken to Kabul and **buried in a garden he had slaughtered** ("Marifat", May 10, 2012);*

Graduation — *Probkin and Svistkov are among those who fell in love with the graduation ceremony ("Youth" 2010, issue 11)*

LEXICAL COMBINATIONS TO GET A HUSBAND or MARRY also have many euphemistic units: to marry, to marry, to marry or marry, to lie down, etc. For example, *Then we talked from one side to the other, I kept answering my aunt's questions about the relatives in the village, who got married, who built a house, who **married a son** and who **gave a daughter** ("Diydor Aziz" 2012, March 29);*

Passing — *At the age of seventeen, they were handed over to my father* ("Diydor Aziz" March 29, 2012), *Tokhtash, who noticed this flaw, did not want to risk his sister's life, and handed her over* ("Youth" 2010, issue 4);

Give to the bridegroom — *When do you think of finding a bridegroom for Dinara? Moreover, Flora is more interested in giving her daughter in marriage — her husband is getting old, and she needs a "to-be" son-in-law* ("Youth" 2010, issue 11);

Getting married — *When my father found out that my mother was not getting well, they left us and soon got married again* ("Diydar Aziz" March 29, 2012), *Getting married early — life's trouble* ("Davr mezoni" March 31, 2012), *Getting married early If I leave, why do I need a house? I thought* ("In the world of law", March 29, 2012);

Marrying — *The daughter of Izhalgan left one side and married another* ("Yoshlik" 2010, issue 6).

Wife or husband — *My spouse's recognition is important to me* ("Darakchi").

Until then, the son consulted with his mother, was in front of her, and after marriage, he was shy in front of his wife, and the mother moved away a little (Diydor Aziz, March 29, 2012).

Kamalmoq also forms a number of synonymous lines. For example, *a girl who became a convict at the age of fifteen* ("Criterium of the Era", March 31, 2012). In many cases, the word **"imprisoned"** is used in the press in the form of **"deprived of freedom"**: *The Termiz City Court of Criminal Cases, which considered this case, found Latofat Mallaeova, a minor, guilty of committing the crime provided for in paragraph "a" of Article 169, Part 4 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and was sentenced to 85 - article was applied and he was deprived of liberty for a period of three years* ("Period criterion", March 31, 2012).

Prostitute — *Well, I earn money, but my house is a place for the homeless* ("Law in the world", March 29, 2012).

It is worth noting that some of the euphemistic units given in the press pages are also an antonymic series. because the softening of the existing event due to the use of euphemisms with the opposite meaning also strengthens the meaning and content through the description.

Antonymous euphemisms are often enclosed in quotation marks in the text. For example, *a five-star "hotel"* ("Khumo", March 21, 2012). The word **hotel** in the text is not used in its original meaning, but in the sense of a **prison**. Here is another example, *I will never forget that day when I went to your house with my first "lover"* ("Yoshlik" 2010, issue 6). The word **beloved** used in this quote means **lover, play**.

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